

Forming Parameters and Mechanical Properties of Cold Extruded MMCs of Aluminium Alloy Matrix

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ABSTRACT

The application of MMCs as structural materials seems promising because of their excellent strength/density ratio. By varying the matrix material, fibre, and particle content, the desired strength and ductility properties can be designed. It is generally understood that the ductility of MMCs is small. They are considered brittle materials. To make use of MMCs on a larger scale, other manufacturing processes besides machining should be employed, e.g. cold extrusion. For the cold extrusion experiments, copper layers (Cu) are generated on the surface of the slugs and interstages by sputtering (PVD) or by plating (galvanic) to test the use of these thin metallic films for the minimization of friction acting on the surface of the workpieces and on the surface of the tool. It is a well-known fact that vapour deposited layers of Cu have excellent properties (solid-film lubrication) with regard to their application as parting layers in cold working of metals. Adhesion and bonding of Cu to the slug surface are quite strong, the values of the shear strength are minor, and the ductility of Cu is sufficient, so that the layer surface can be increased to more than ten times its original value without rupture. In those cases where Cu layers are used as parting coatings, a MoS₂ spray is applied on top of the coating as a lubricant. Components under mass production conditions were cold extruded and the forming parameters, e.g. extrusion force, the surface quality of the components, and the coefficient of friction (tribological properties), were under test. Fatigue tests, uni-axial compression tests, and tensile tests of cold extruded workpieces were carried out to prove that the mechanical properties of these cold extruded MMCs are increased to a greater value compared with the as-received conditions.

MATERIAL DATA AND TEST SET-UP

The tested MMCs of aluminium alloy matrices AA6082 or AA230A were produced by hot extrusion of aluminium alloy powder mixed with SiC powder-reinforcement in a powder-metallurgical process (PM-MMCs). The material data of these tested MMCs of aluminium alloy matrix, i.e. chemical composition and mechanical properties (tensile and uni-axial isothermal compression test) were presented earlier [1, 2].

The extrusion tests were carried out by means of a hydraulic press with a nominal force of 1,000 kN. For forward bar extrusion (FBE) and forward tube extrusion (FTE), the specimens (slugs) of the tested composites have an outer diameter $d_0 = 24.7$ mm, an inner diameter $d_2 = 10$ mm, and a height $h_0 = 30$ mm. The specimens for forward cup extrusion (FCE) have a diameter $d_0 = 24.7$ mm and a height $h_0 = 24$ mm. To reduce the maximum value of extrusion force, the slugs for FBE and FTE are tapered with half the die angle $\alpha/2 = 45^\circ$ on one face side.

The punches and the dies are made of high speed steel. The dies are reinforced by double shrink rings and the inner diameter of the dies is $d_0 = 25.1$ mm.

REQUIREMENTS ON COLD EXTRUDED COMPONENTS (MMCs)

To prove that by cold extrusion MMC components could be produced under industrial conditions (application of MMCs as structural materials), several aspects were under study, see Figure 1. It is clearly indicated, that only crack-free components and workpieces with a very good surface quality can be accepted.

Application of MMCs as structural materials.

Requirements on cold extruded components:

- I: Production of crack-free components
- II: Cold extrusion of components with a very good surface quality
- III: Development of lubrication systems for mass production
- IV: Testing of lubrication systems (mass production of components)
- V: Mechanical properties of cold extruded components (hardness tests, tensile tests, compression tests => static tests)
- VI: Mechanical properties (fatigue tests => dynamic tests)

Figure 1.

Requirements and tests on cold extruded components of MMC.

Additionally, the results of hardness tests, tensile tests, compression tests, and fatigue tests must ensure that the mechanical

properties of the cold extruded components of MMCs have a greater value than the MMCs in the as-received condition ($\epsilon_A = 0$).

FBE, CP
CP = 650 MPa
do = 24.7 mm
ho = 30 mm

Lubrication system:
PVD-Cu (18 μ m) +
Unimoly C 220 (MoS₂)
**FORWARD
BAR EX-
TRUSION
OF PM-
MMCs**

$\epsilon_A = 0.3$: 1 - AA6082; $\epsilon_A = 0.5$: 3 - AA6082; $\epsilon_A = 0.7$: 5 - AA6082
2 - AA230A; 4 - AA230A; 6 - AA230A

Figure 2. Influence of matrix material; FBE, CP of PM-MMCs [1, 2].

The different types of matrix materials and also the percentage of reinforcement material will have an influence on the forming parameters, on the hardness, the tensile strength, on the flow stress, and on the fatigue strength of the cold forged components, see. Figure 1. The expected brittle behaviour of the matrix material AA-230A is verified by the force-travel diagrams. Figure 2 represents the comparison between AA6082 and AA230A for different values of strain ϵ_A . Both materials are reinforced by 25 % SiCp. For the extrusion of AA230A (curve 6) with the strain of $\epsilon_A = 0.7$ a maximum value of extrusion pressure 1,505 MPa is required while the corresponding value for the alloy AA6082 is 1,416 MPa only. The difference between curve 5 and curve 6 is approx. 6 %.

FORWARD TUBE AND FORWARD CUP EXTRUSION OF PM-MMCs

Forward tube extrusion (FTE) is a more difficult cold forging process than FBE [3], because of the additional frictional forces acting on the mandrel and because of the phenomenon of fish-skin surface on the inner bore. Figure 3 (left side) shows the force-travel diagram of a PM-MMC for FTE, CP with an areal strain $\epsilon_A = 1.25$ and with a counter pressure of CP = 400 MPa. The general characteristic of the diagram corresponds to the diagram of conventional, i.e. low carbon steels, materials deformed by cold extrusion. The surface of the inner bore shows no sign of development of fish-skin. The inner and outer surface of the components are free of cracks and the surface quality corresponds to that value which can be expected in general in cold extrusion [3].

Figure 3. FTE,CP & FCE,CP of PM-MMCs [1, 2].

To obtain more information about the general behaviour of the tested PM-MMCs in cold extrusion, not only experiments on steady-state forward (FBE,CP & FTE,CP) extrusion are carried out, but also the non-steady state process of forward cup extrusion (FCE,CP) is under study, see Figure 3, right side [1, 2]. The extrusion-force vs. punch-travel diagram (after the FCE,CP) shows that the value of the extrusion force is increased from approx. 400 kN to 450 kN if the percentage of SiC particles is increased from 15 % to 25 %.

SURFACE QUALITY OF COLD EXTRUDED MMC-COMPONENTS; FCE,CP

To ensure that MMCs can be used as structural materials, the surface quality of the slugs and the surface quality of the cold extruded components must be experimentally determined. In this case the most difficult cold forging process FCE,CP was under test. In Figure 4 it is clearly indicated that, by using a copper-layer (galvanic; approx. 15 μm thickness), an average roughness height $R_{ab} = 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ of the slugs in the non-deformed condition was found. The average roughness height after FCE,CP with an areal strain $\epsilon_A = 0.6$ is reduced to 0.17 μm , see Figure 4. Under the same condition, 60 workpieces were cold extruded which show no sign of wear (between container and outer side of the cup or punch and inner side of the cup).

Figure 4. Relative Surface Improvement ϵ_{Ra} after FCE,CP of PM-MMC.

Figure 4 shows also that during the FCE,CP tests of the 60 workpieces the relative surface improvement ϵ_{Ra} after FCE,CP was found to be between 0.70 and 0.95.

PARTIAL COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION; FBE

During FBE, the friction force F_0 acts in the plane of contact between slug and die bore surface d_0 , see Figure 5. If the height $h_{0,1}$ of the slug is increased to a greater value $h_{0,2}$, an increase (ΔF_0) of the maximum extrusion force must be expected. This difference of extrusion force permits calculation of the partial coefficient of friction μ_0 , which describes the frictional conditions in the die bore (d_0). The normal pressure p_0 can be calculated by the extrusion pressure p_{p0} and by the flow stress $\bar{\sigma}_0$, see Eqn(2) after TRESCA in Figure 5 and [3].

Figure 5. Determination of the partial coefficient of friction μ_0 ; FBE.

In Figure 6, the corresponding extrusion-force vs. punch-travel diagrams for FBE,CP of a PM-MMC are shown. In the case of FBE,CP, in the quasi-steady region of the F_u - S_u -diagram the extrusion force is a nearly linear function of the land height of the die. Due to the increasing values of the counter force F_C from 81 kN to 162 kN (increasing counter pres-

Figure 6. Extrusion force vs. punch-travel diagrams & partial coefficient of friction μ_0 ; FBE,CP of AA6082 + 25 % SiCp.

sure), the extrusion force F_U and the extrusion pressure p_p are also increased. Figure 6 (right side) indicates that, by making use of a higher extrusion pressure, the normal pressure at the area of contact d_0 is also increased, see Eqn(2). This fact proves the well-known relationship that with increasing normal pressure the partial coefficient of friction is reduced [3].

Having the composite AA6082 + 25 % SiCp under test, the average partial coefficient $\bar{\mu}_0$ is reduced from 0.06 to 0.025. This result indicates, by comparison with the coefficients of friction for the cold extrusion of low carbon steels [$\mu \approx 0.1$; 3] that for the cold extrusion of PM-MMCs very small partial coefficients of friction μ_0 , i.e. small values of friction force F_0 , are acting in the area of contact (d_0) of the die bore.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COLD EXTRUDED MMCs

For the description of the mechanical (static) properties, hardness tests, tensile tests, and compression tests were carried out. The values of vickers hardness HV2 of the specimens before extrusion ($\epsilon_A = 0$) and of the components after extrusion FBE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 0.3$ & 0.7) and after FTE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 1.25$) are plotted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Influence of material composition and of areal strain on the values of vickers hardness before and after cold extrusion.

It shows that the values of the vickers hardness after FBE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 0.7$) are greater than the values after FTE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 1.25$). By means of an increased counter pressure CP (CP = 400 MPa to CP = 650 MPa) the values of the hardness of the extruded components are also increased, due to more homogeneous state of stress by using a greater counter pressure [2].

Figure 8. Vickers hardness HV2 of the cold extruded PM-MMC AA6082 + 25 % SiCp after FBE,CP & FTE,CP; parallel to axis.

Figure 8 shows the values of vickers hardness after FBE,CP and after FTE,CP. This diagram indicates that, with increasing areal strain ϵ_A , the values of the vickers hardness are also increased. In the case of FTE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 1.25$), the hardness of the workpiece, in accor-

dance with the micrographs [1, 2], is more uniform over the cross-section than the hardness after FBE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 0.3$). This is due to the small value of strain $\epsilon_A = 0.3$ which is inhomogeneous over the cross-section of the extruded part of the components [1, 2].

For comparison purposes, tensile tests of as-received PM-MMCs ($\epsilon_A = 0$) and of the cold extruded components (FTE,CP, $\epsilon_A = 1.25$) were carried out.

Figure 9. Influence of material composition and of areal strain on the values of ultimate tensile strength.

It is shown in Figure 9, that the ultimate tensile strength of the cold forged components is increased to a greater value compared with the as-received materials ($\epsilon_A = 0$).

Figure 10. Influence of areal strain on the flow stress; PM-MMC [2].

In Figure 10 the influence of areal strain ϵ_A on the flow stress for a PM-MMC after extrusion is demonstrated. Curve 2 of Figure 10 represents the flow curve of AA6082 + 15 % SiCp after FBE,CP with an areal strain $\epsilon_A = 0.3$. The cylindrical specimen for the uni-axial isothermal compression test is taken from the extruded part of a component. The flow curve of the material in the undeformed as-received condition is plotted for reference reasons as curve 1. The cold extruded material has an ultimate limit strain $\epsilon_{h,max} \approx 0.98$.

Figure 10 also shows that the value of the flow stress of the undeformed PM-MMC (curve 1) at a strain $\epsilon_h = 0.3$ is nearly identical to the flow stress of the extruded material (curve 2) at the beginning of the compression test ($\epsilon_h = 0$). The flow stress of the cold extruded specimen is increased from approx. 330 MPa to approx. 415 MPa ($\epsilon_{h,max} \approx 0.98$). It is evident that the work hardening exponent of curve 2 ($n_2 = 0.13$) is smaller than the n-value of curve 1 ($n_1 = 0.17$), see Figure 10. The results of the three static tests of the cold extruded MMCs prove that the mechanical properties i.e. the vickers hardness, the tensile strength, and the flow stress are greater than the values of the undeformed composites.

FATIGUE TESTS

To ensure that cold extruded components could be used as structural materials, specimens machined out of workpieces after FBE,CP ($\epsilon_A = 0.9$), out of workpieces after FTE,CP (ϵ_A

Figure 11. Fatigue strength $\Delta\sigma$ vs. number of cycles N diagrams of PM-composite AA6082 + 25 % SiCp.

= 1.25), and for reference reasons an undeformed PM-MMC ($\epsilon_A = 0$) were under study with regard to their mechanical properties under dynamic load. Fatigue tests were carried out and the $\Delta\sigma$ -N curves are plotted in Figure 11. It indicates that, if workpieces (FTE,CP, $\epsilon_A = 1.25$) were under dynamic load, a maximum strength 130 MPa (curve 3) can be expected.

Figure 12. Fatigue tests of PM-composite AA6082 + 15 % SiCp.

rimentally determined. By using specimens, machined out of cold extruded components (FBE,CP, $\epsilon_A = 0.9$), only a maximum strength of 110 MPa was found (curve 2). Figure 11 shows also that, with increasing areal strain, the negative slope of the curves is increased. Generally it was found that the fatigue test making use of cold extruded workpieces revealed better fatigue properties ($\Delta\sigma$ -N curves) than the values of the machined specimens. In the case of FBE and FTE, it can be assumed that the inhomogeneous condition of strain ϵ_v on the component will have a great influence of the static and dynamic properties of the forged components, by using of specimen machined out of extruded workpieces, see Figures 7 to 12. However, the minimum values of average surface height R_a of cold extruded workpieces, see Figure 4 (FCE,CP), will have a great influence on fatigue properties, too.

GRAIN STRUCTURE AFTER FATIGUE TESTS

Figure 13 shows a micrograph (REM) of the composite AA6082 + 25 % SiCp in the undeformed condition ($\epsilon_A = 0$). In this Figure, only a very small plastic deformation of the alu-

Figure 13 and 14: Micrographs (REM) of AA6082 + 25 % SiCp before (left) and after fatigue test (right part).

minium alloy matrix was found. It is obvious that, in the undeformed condition, there are areas with low content of particles and areas of particle accumulation (clusters).

Figure 14 (FBE, CP, $\epsilon_A = 0.9$; fatigue test, $N > 10^5$) shows, that the ductility of the aluminium alloy matrix is increased due to the fact that, after the cold extrusion operation with an areal strain $\epsilon_A = 0.9$, the material is now more uniform.

CONCLUSIONS

For the application of MMCs as structural materials several technological aspects were under study. For the production of crack-free components and for the minimisation of friction a tribological system can be used consisting of a copper layer (PVD-Cu or galvanic-Cu) of approx. $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $18 \mu\text{m}$ thickness and an MoS_2 spray as a lubricant.

MMCs with a matrix of AA6082 or AA230A (PM-MMCs), and with a reinforcement of 15 or 25 volumetric weight % SiC particles can be successfully deformed by cold extrusion.

Forward bar extrusion, forward tube extrusion, and forward cup extrusion tests were carried out making use of a counter pressure, by which a high hydrostatic pressure was introduced in the forming zone. By this means, the workability of the MMCs was increased to such an extent that crack-free components were extruded.

The tribological and the mechanical properties of the cold extruded PM-MMCs were under test. It was found that the vickers hardness (HV2), the tensile strength (R_m), the flow stress ($\bar{\sigma}$), and the fatigue strength $\Delta\sigma$ of the cold extruded components are increased due to work hardening.

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